

FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN THE FAMILY

Atamurodov Shodiyar Oralovich

JDPI. Docent of the faculty of Physical culture

Hasanov Anvar Toxirovich

JDPU Faculty of Physical Culture senior lecturer

Abstract: *The article describes how children form a healthy lifestyle in the family.*

Key words: *Healthy lifestyle, preschool, family, physical education, educator, teacher, knowledge, skill, qualification.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассказывается, как дети формируют здоровый образ жизни в семье.*

Ключевые слова: *Здоровый образ жизни, дошкольный, семья, физическая культура, воспитатель, педагог, знания, навык, квалификация.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada bolalar oilada sogʻlom turmush tarzini qanday shakllantirishlari tasvirlangan.*

Kalit soʻzlar: *Sogʻlom turmush tarzi, maktabgacha tarbiya, oila, jismoniy tarbiya, tarbiyachi, oʻqituvchi, bilim, mahorat, malaka.*

Today, the formation of a healthy generation is one of the most important tasks. First of all, the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the creation of various living conditions, the establishment of a material basis for raising a healthy generation, ie the adoption of state programs with economic and financial support and their effective implementation are the main basis for educating a harmoniously developed generation. is a testament to his focus on youth, family, and a healthy generation.

Creating the necessary conditions for building a healthy and strong family, which is an important, decisive link in the upbringing of the younger generation, formed as children, individuals, nurtured in the spirit of love for the Fatherland, national and universal values, worthy representatives of their people; The issues of establishing the principles of a healthy lifestyle among young people, the implementation of comprehensive measures to protect them from drugs, dirt, the dangers and harmful effects of various evils of the inferior "popular culture" from the outside.

Today, the issue of forming a healthy lifestyle among young people is the main direction of modern pedagogical research, and a number of scientific researches are being conducted in this field in our country and abroad. In particular, S.Nishonova, M.Inomova, O.Musurmonova, V.Karimova, D.Sharipova, D.Khalikov, E.Seytkhalilov, M.Tairova, E.Sh. Pedagogical psychologists and philosophers such as Yusupov and J.Tulenov conducted scientific research, while D.Sharipova, M.Tairova, E.Seytkhalilov, A.Isimova, F.Abdurahimova studied the medical direction of the formation of a healthy lifestyle. Our observations show that the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the family of young people, especially preschool children, has not been studied as a separate area of research, but some issues of healthy lifestyle formation, the formation of healthy lifestyle skills in them have been studied by researchers R.Kh. Juraev, N.Shodiev, D Covered by Sharipova, E.Seytkhalilov, M.Tairova, M.F.Ziyaeva, N.Jalilova, M.Tilovov.

- Preschool education, family and community partnerships are important in shaping a healthy lifestyle for preschool children in the family [3]. On the basis of this cooperation, the activities of preschool education institution, family, neighborhood, preschool children in the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the family will be significantly improved; work forms and methods are enriched; mutual experience is exchanged; a critical and imitative approach to work emerges; Repetition and repetition are not allowed in educational work; quality indicators of the educational process grow; an integrated mechanism of cooperation will be created; there is a need of the time in the upbringing of preschool children in a healthy lifestyle in the family, there is an opportunity to conduct educational work at a scientific, practical, high level.

- The effectiveness of interaction in the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the family of preschool children has its own characteristics [4]. They are:

- The knowledge, skills and abilities formed in preschool educational institutions will be strengthened, enriched and improved;

- The content, form and methods of educational work are organized not on the basis of existing achievements, but on the basis of shortcomings, interests and aspirations of preschool children;

- Consistency, consistency in activities, the advantage of relying on public opinion;

- Public monitoring of the evaluation of the results of educational work.

When studying and analyzing the current state of the problem, it became clear that a negative approach to the effectiveness of educational activities carried out in collaboration with the family, community, preschool education institution is required.

- Ineffectiveness of educational work aimed at increasing the knowledge of preschool children in the spiritual, moral, medical and social preparation for school life, the formation of a healthy lifestyle;
- Insufficient number of booklets, brochures and notes and methodological materials aimed at promoting a healthy lifestyle of preschool children in families and MTCs;
- parents do not pay enough attention to the knowledge and realization of the child's lifestyle, talents, interests and abilities in the family;
- Insufficient attention of preschool children to a healthy lifestyle in the family, national traditions, universal values formed over the centuries;
- Insufficient level of medical literacy of parents and educators;
- ignorance of educators about the forms and methods of educational work on the formation of a healthy lifestyle;
- Lack of research on this problem in pedagogy, psychology, physical education, etc.

In order to prevent these shortcomings, the plan of educational work carried out in collaboration with families, neighborhoods, preschools, focused on a specific aspect of a healthy lifestyle, organized on the basis of demand and needs, formed on the basis of national and universal values, age and individual psychological characteristics. The organization of educational work in traditional and non-traditional forms, taking into account the problems of sanitary and hygienic condition of families, is also a pedagogical requirement.

Experience has shown that a special chain is formed for preschool children to form a healthy lifestyle in the family, and if there is a gap in any of them, it is impossible to achieve the expected result in ensuring continuity in educational work.

Based on the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the family of preschool children, the desired result can not be achieved without the interaction of the family, neighborhood, preschool education institution [2]. The subjects directly involved in the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the family of preschool children closely assist them in organizing, managing, directing, evaluating and monitoring the results of educational activities.

The content of this chain and its effectiveness depends on the topic chosen for the educational event, scientific and methodological resources. They are: scientific-methodical, popular literature on human spiritual and physical health, healthy lifestyle; heritage of ancient and medieval thinkers, internet materials; advanced work experience, examples of scientific achievements; visual aids (posters, booklets, handouts).

The success of educational activities based on the chain of cooperation depends on the level of preparation, worldview, relevance, responsiveness, level of knowledge, experience, self-study, level of responsibility and opportunity, creativity, attitude to work, foresight, dedication, attitude to news. .

In the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the family of preschool children:

- Supporting the interests and aspirations of preschool children, strengthening the role of state and public organizations in solving their problems;
- Carrying out regular monitoring of the work carried out in collaboration with the family, community, preschool education institution on the formation of a healthy lifestyle in preschool children in the family and the establishment of appropriate measures, strengthening their control;
- maintaining the health of family members, ensuring the healthy physical growth of preschool children;
- comprehensive spiritual, spiritual and moral upbringing of children in the family;
- Ensuring that children are involved in physical culture and sports;
- upbringing children in the spirit of respect for national and universal values, devotion to family traditions and customs;
- Creating a culture of interaction between family members, a healthy spiritual environment between spouses, parents and children, the formation of a healthy lifestyle;
- Regularly inform children about healthy lifestyles;
- It is necessary to carry out educational activities to raise the awareness of young people on issues such as achieving full economic security of the family.

Also, in ensuring the effectiveness of the content of cooperation:

- Special attention to the importance of a healthy lifestyle, the role of physical education and sports in human life, the impact of ecology on human health, the sanctity of marriage among young people, the preparation of young people for family life, the preparation of young people for family life in educational institutions. it is necessary to strengthen the demand for courses.

In conclusion, the solution of the above-mentioned social problems, the development of effective research technologies for the formation of a healthy lifestyle with preschool children and regular monitoring will determine their role in ensuring the development of society.

REFERENCES

1. "Ilk qadam" Davlat dasturi. T.: 2018.
2. Maxkamjonov K.M., Tulenova X. Farzandlarimiz soglom bulishini istasangiz. –T.: 1995.
3. Munavvarov A.K. Oila pedagogikasi. –T.: O‘qituvchi, 1994.
4. Yusupova P. Maktabgacha tarbiya pedagogikasi. –T.: O‘qituvchi, 1993.
5. Yakhshilikov, Sanjar. (2023). The Impact of a donor’s domestic political economy on its policy and practice of development cooperation comparing to the impact of international norms and principles. *Frontline Social Sciences and History Journal*. 03. 32-40. 10.37547/social-fsshj-03-01-05.
6. Xasanov, Anvar. (2017). Физическая культура и спорт как важный аспект в формировании личности. *Форум молодых ученых*. 5. 425-428.
7. Xasanov, Anvar. (2017). Физическая культура-надежда natsii. *Форум молодых ученых*. 5. 591.
8. Xasanov, Anvar & Mamanazarova, A. (2022). Website: www.sjird.journalspark.org WRESTLING PREPARATION PROCESS IN SPORTS SCHOOLS. *SPECTRUM Journal of Gender and Children Studies*. 19. 174.
9. Yakhshilikov, Sanjar. (2023). UNAVOIDABLE CLASHES: EXPLORING THE IMPLICATIONS OF A CHINA-RUSSIA ALLIANCE ON GLOBAL GEOPOLITICS. *Austral Brazilian Journal of Strategy & International Relations*. 12. 198-209. 10.22456/2238-6912.131366.
10. Nurmatov, Eldor. (2023). *Maqola Jurnal chet el.*
11. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). METHODS OF FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE FOR CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY.
12. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). РОЛЬ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МОТИВАЦИИ.
13. Nurmatov, Eldor. (2023). *Maqola Jurnal chet el.*
14. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). РОЛЬ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МОТИВАЦИИ.
15. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). ORGANIZING TOURIST TRIPS WITH STUDENTS Anvar Toxirovich Hasanov JDPU. "Physical culture" faculty. *Journal of Physical Education*.
16. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). DUTIES OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS ON THE FIELD Anvar Takhirovich Hasanov JDPU. "Physical culture" faculty.

17. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). Forming a conscious attitude of adolescents towards their health. 10.13140/RG.2.2.25438.41289.

18. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). РОЛЬ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МОТИВАЦИИ.

19. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS Anvar Takhirovich Hasanov JDPU. "Physical culture" faculty.

20. Atamurodov, Shodiyor. (2023). ТУРИСТИК САЁХАТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ.

21. Nomozov, Abdurashid. (2023). Sogʻlom turmush tarziga sportning ahamiyati hamda oʻrni qanchalik muhimligini taʼsir etuvchi omillari..